

(E)-5,5'-(3-Phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione] : Synthesis, characterization, crystal structure and antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : The title compound (A) has been synthesized by the reaction of 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil with cinnamaldehyde (mixture of *Z* and *E* isomer) in aqueous media followed by recrystallization from 98% ethanolic solution. The compound is characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR, UV-Vis spectroscopy and single crystal X-ray diffraction. The compound crystallizes in the monoclinic space group with *a* = 11.4666(9) Å, *b* = 12.3330(11) Å, *c* = 14.7670(12) Å, β = 99.632(8)° and *Z* = 4. In the crystal structure, molecules are linked by N–H···O hydrogen bonds forming a linear 1–D chain and the structure is further stabilized by weak C–H···O and π–π stacking interactions. The title compound has also been screened for antifungal and antibacterial activity which shows important antibacterial property.

Keywords : Uracil derivatives, synthesis, crystal structure, ¹H NMR, biological property.

Introduction

The field of crystal engineering is regarded as a comprehensive subject which deals with modeling, synthesis, evaluation and utilization of crystalline solids having desired functions along with construction of fascinating topological architectures^{1,2}. The advancement of crystal engineering as a research field has ushered significant interest in the study of intermolecular interactions and their subsequent use in the formation of solid-state structures. The arrangement of molecules in the solid-state underpins much of modern crystal engineering and thus the subject continues to be driven by the understanding of intermolecular interactions and their use in trying to control solid-state structures. Several interactions are very commonly used by chemists to construct supramolecular assemblies, such as hydrogen-bonding³, π–π stacking⁴, cation–π⁵ and C–H···π⁶ contacts.

Uracil (U) and its derivatives, constituents of the genetic material, play a pivotal role in basic biological processes. From crystal engineering perspective, uracil based compounds are interesting because of their ability to form hydrogen bonds using the endocyclic nitrogen and exocyclic

oxygen centers. Often uracil based supramolecules self-assemble utilizing arrays of multiple hydrogen bonds for holding together the individual building blocks⁷. The bioactivity of 5-substituted uracils induces exceptional interest in their biochemistry and pharmacology and they are the most interesting and studied uracils. 5-Fluorouracil has been in use as chemotherapy agent the treatment of malignancies including colorectal and breast cancers⁸. Being the most effective inhibitor of 4-aminobutirataminotransferase, 5-ioduracil is an important antimetabolite. 5-Cyanouracil exhibit cellular activity and has been shown to inhibit pyrimidine catabolism *in vivo*⁹. The biological and physicochemical properties of these compounds depend on the ability of molecules to form hydrogen bonding and also to participate in π-stacking interactions. The synthetic exploitation of nucleophilic double bond of uracil continues to generate interest among researchers in view of great variety of potential products. Though many reports are available in literature for the functionalization of uracil but most of these suffer from harsh reaction condition or longer synthetic pathway¹⁰.

In view of the importance of multitopic uracil linkers

as building blocks for supramolecular architectures and considering their bioactivity, design and synthesis functionalized uracil moieties are essential. In our earlier paper we reported synthesis and crystal structures of various aryl/alkyl/heteroaryl bis-(6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil-5-yl)methanes in water¹¹. But crystal structure of the title compound (A) could not be obtained. In the present study, we report herein synthesis, characterization and crystal structure determination of (*E*)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione] by the reaction of 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil with cinnamaldehyde (mixture of *Z* and *E* isomer) and its corresponding spectral and crystallographic analysis (Scheme 1). Potential antimicrobial property of the newly synthesized compound also has been explored.

Scheme 1. Reaction route for the synthesis.

Results and discussion

X-Ray analysis :

The molecular structure of the title compound with the atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 1. Bond distances and bond angles are shown in Tables 1 and 2. In the compound, the dihedral angle between the two uracil rings A (N1/N4/C6-C8) and B (N3/N4/C6-C8) is 60.44(14)° with centroid-centroid separation of 5.069(2) Å. The torsion angles involving the bonds connecting the two uracil moieties C2-C3-C5-C8 and C7-C8-C5-C3 are -110.22° and -98.36° respectively. In ring A, the C4-N5 bond [1.337(5) Å] and in ring B, C9-N6 bond [1.350(5) Å] is intermediate between that of a single and double bond. The C-N bonds (C4-N5 and C9-N6) linked with a free amino group are shorter than the cyclic C-N bonds, but the C-N bonds (C18-N1, C19-N2, C20-N3 and C21-N4) linked with free methyl group are longer than the cyclic C-N bonds. The exocyclic C-O distances vary from 1.223(5) Å to 1.255(5) Å. In ring A, C2-O2 bond length is longer than C1-O1, likewise in ring B, C7-O4 is

Fig. 1. View of the molecule with displacement ellipsoids drawn at 50% probability level.

Table 1. Bond distances for non-hydrogen atoms

O2-C2	1.250(5)	N6-C9	1.350(5)
O4-C7	1.255(5)	C9-C8	1.375(5)
O1-C1	1.223(5)	C7-C8	1.406(5)
O3-C6	1.231(5)	C3-C4	1.371(5)
N1-C4	1.382(5)	C3-C2	1.414(5)
N1-C1	1.388(5)	C3-C5	1.524(5)
N1-C18	1.463(5)	C8-C5	1.519(5)
N2-C2	1.397(5)	C5-C10	1.514(5)
N2-C1	1.371(5)	C10-C11	1.318(5)
N2-C19	1.459(5)	C12-C11	1.474(6)
N3-C9	1.379(5)	C12-C13	1.371(6)
N3-C6	1.379(5)	C12-C17	1.394(5)
N3-C20	1.479(4)	C13-C14	1.379(6)
N4-C7	1.399(5)	C17-C16	1.390(6)
N4-C6	1.375(5)	C14-C15	1.353(6)
N4-C21	1.464(5)	C15-C16	1.379(7)
N5-C4	1.337(5)		

Table 2. Bond angles (°) for non-hydrogen atoms

C4-N1-C1	122.4(4)	N5-C4-C3	123.1(4)
C4-N1-C18	120.8(4)	C3-C4-N1	120.4(4)
C1-N1-C18	116.7(4)	O2-C2-N2	117.3(4)
C2-N2-C19	119.7(4)	O2-C2-C3	124.9(4)
C1-N2-C2	123.7(4)	N2-C2-C3	117.8(4)
C1-N2-C19	116.5(4)	C8-C5-C3	117.0(3)
C9-N3-C6	121.8(4)	C10-C5-C3	115.2(3)
C9-N3-C20	121.6(4)	C10-C5-C8	113.1(3)

Table-2 (contd.)

C6-N3-C20	116.5(4)	C11-C10-C5	129.2(4)
C7-N4-C21	119.1(4)	C13-C12-C11	121.6(4)
C6-N4-C7	123.7(4)	C13-C12-C17	117.8(5)
C6-N4-C21	117.1(4)	C17-C12-C11	120.6(5)
N6-C9-N3	115.9(4)	O1-C1-N1	121.4(4)
N6-C9-C8	123.1(4)	O1-C1-N2	122.4(5)
C8-C9-N3	121.0(4)	N2-C1-N1	116.2(4)
O4-C7-N4	117.3(4)	O3-C6-N3	121.7(4)
O4-C7-C8	125.2(4)	O3-C6-N4	121.7(5)
N4-C7-C8	117.5(4)	N4-C6-N3	116.7(4)
C4-C3-C2	119.3(4)	C10-C11-C12	124.1(4)
C4-C3-C5	124.6(4)	C12-C13-C14	121.8(5)
C2-C3-C5	116.1(4)	C16-C17-C12	120.3(5)
C9-C8-C7	119.2(4)	C15-C14-C13	120.0(6)
C9-C8-C5	119.0(4)	C14-C15-C16	120.2(6)
C7-C8-C5	121.8(3)	C15-C16-C17	119.8(5)
N5-C4-N1	116.5(4)		

somewhat longer than C6-O3. In the uracil ring C3-C4 and C8-C9 bonds are shorter than C2-C3 and C8-C7 bonds indicating true double bond character. At the same time, the lengths of the three bonds involving the C5 (C5-C3, C5-C8 and C5-C10) are representing the single bonds, somewhat longer than the single C-C bond. The C10-C11 double bond distance 1.320(7) Å is significantly shorter for its type.

Both intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonds between an amino N-H group and carbonyl-O atom are foreseen in the structure (Table 3). Due to the presence of intramolecular N-H...O hydrogen bonding, the two amino groups of uracil rings are oriented in opposite direction, i.e. they are magnetically non-equivalent. It can be seen from the packing diagram (Fig. 2) that intermolecular N-H...O hydrogen bonds lead to the formation of a linear 1-D chain of molecules. The stability of molecular packing also arises from π - π stacking interactions (Fig. 3). The linear chains are held together by the weak C-H...O interactions (Fig. 4).

Table 3. Hydrogen bonding parameter (Å, °)

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
N5-H5A...O4	0.86	2.01	2.856(4)	166.9
N5-H5B...O2 ^a	0.86	2.47	3.279(5)	156.1
N6-H6A...O2	0.86	2.18	3.028(4)	167.1
N6-H6B...O4 ^b	0.86	2.21	3.010(4)	154.7

Symmetry codes : ^a1-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z; ^b+x, 1/2-y, -1/2+z.

IR studies :

The IR spectrum (Fig. S1) of the compound (A) contains a set of characteristic absorption bands : 3390–3214 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{N-H})$], 3097–2841 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{C-H})$], 1688 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{C=O})$], 1594–1497 cm^{-1} [ν , pyrimidine ring, $\nu(\text{C=N})$, $\nu(\text{C=C})$], 1378 cm^{-1} [ν , pyrimidine ring, $\delta_s(\text{CH}_3)$], 1245–1145 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{NCN})$, $\nu(\text{CCN})$, $\nu(\text{CNC})$] and 1053–699 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{C-C})$, $\nu(\text{C-N})$, $\sigma(\text{CH}_3)$, $\sigma(\text{CH}_2)$]. IR spectral data thus clearly lend support to the structure determined by X-ray diffraction method.

NMR studies :

¹H NMR spectrum (Fig. S2) of compound A was recorded in CDCl_3 . In the spectrum, δ_{H} 3.31 (3H, s) indicates the presence of three equivalent H-atoms which are in the -NCH₃ group situated in between the two keto groups and δ_{H} 3.35 (3H, s) indicates another set of three equivalent H-atoms present in the -NCH₃ group situated in between the keto and amino group. δ_{H} 3.42 (6H, s) corresponds to the six equivalent H-atoms of the two other -NCH₃ group. δ_{H} 5.16 (1H, s) indicates the presence of one H-atom which is in the -CH group attached to two pyrimidine groups. δ_{H} 6.27 (br, s) stands for the equivalent H-atoms of the amino group. δ_{H} 6.70 (1H, d) corresponds to the presence of alkene hydrogen atom closer to the pyrimidine group whereas δ_{H} 6.74 (1H, d) stands for the alkene hydrogen atom closer to the phenyl ring. At last, the value 7.15–7.34 (5H, m) are for the five equivalent H-atoms of the phenyl ring.

Electronic spectra :

The UV-Visible spectrum (10^{-6} mol L⁻¹ solution) of the title compound (A) was recorded in ethanol solution. Compound A exhibits a strong absorption band at 262 nm (Fig. S3) which may be considered to originate from intramolecule π - π^* transition.

Antimicrobial studies :

The newly synthesized (*E*)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione] (A) is found to possess good antibacterial properties (MIC 12.5–235 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). On the other hand, the compound showed least growth inhibition against fungi. An organized glance of the data is illustrated in Tables 4–6. As the title compound was inactive against the tested fungi strains, the MIC data is not tabulated. Due to the poor solubility of title compound in common organic solvents

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of the molecule showing the hydrogen bonding viewed along the “*b*” direction.

Fig. 3. Depiction of π - π stacking interaction in the compound. The angle between the planes is 4.43° , the centroid-centroid distance is 3.637 \AA and the shift distance is 1.237 \AA .

Fig. 4. C-H...O interaction in the molecule.

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Fig. S1. IR spectrum of compound (A).

Fig. S2. The ¹H NMR spectra of (*E*)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione].

Fig. S3. UV-Visible spectrum of compound A.

Table 4. Antibacterial activities of the title compound (A) against both Gram (+) and Gram (-) bacteria

Test compound	Zone of inhibition against						
	SA	BS	EC	PA1	PA2	PA3	PA4
A	13	14	15	10	14	10	15
Streptomycin	24	28	26	26	26	27	25

SA = *Staphylococcus aureus*; BS = *Bacillus subtilis*; EC = *E. coli*; PA1 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7812); PA2 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7814); PA3 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7816); PA4 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7818).

Table 5. Antifungal activities of the title compound (A) against fungi strains

Test compound	Zone of inhibition against	
	CA	FO
A	-	-
Clotrimazole	11	10

CA = *Candida albicans* (MTCC 227); FO = *Fusarium oxysporium* (MTCC 284).

Table 6. MIC values for the title compound (A)

Test compound	MIC values ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) against						
	SA	BS	EC	PA1	PA2	PA3	PA4
A	180	50	12.5	200	12.5	235	25

SA = *Staphylococcus aureus*; BS = *Bacillus subtilis*; EC = *E. coli*; PA1 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7812); PA2 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7814); PA3 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7816); PA4 = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7818).

or water, it was dissolved and tested for corresponding antimicrobial activities in a 10% DMSO (v/v) aqueous solution¹². It was also found from literature that 10% DMSO (v/v) was used for antimicrobial and other bio-

logical activities¹³⁻¹⁷. Before our study of the antimicrobial activities we first screened the percentage of DMSO (ranging from 1 to 15%, v/v) that is tolerated by cells or not. The presence of 10% DMSO (v/v) had no detectable effect on bacterial growth of both the Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Again, it was also noticeable that different organisms responded differently to the same concentration of a given solvent¹⁸. Here, we tested bacteria and fungi comfortable with 10% DMSO (v/v) and showed no detectable effect on growth.

Experimental

Materials and measurements :

Chemicals used were all reagent grade products. Melting point was determined with a Büchi 504 apparatus. IR spectrum was recorded as KBr pellets with a Nicolet (Impact 410) FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectrum was recorded with a JNM ECS 400 MHz NMR spectrophotometer (JEOL) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the internal standard. Reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography using aluminium sheets with silica gel 60 F254 (Merck). Elemental analyses were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyser (2400 series II). Electronic spectrum of the compound was recorded using Shimadzu spectrophotometer UV-1800.

Synthesis of (E)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis-[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione] :

Distilled water (30 mL) was added to 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil (155 mg, 1 mmol) in a 100 mL round-bottomed flask and the mixture was stirred at room temperature until all the 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil had dissolved. Cinnamaldehyde (63 μL , 0.5 mmol) was added dropwise to the 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil solution with constant stirring and then after 3 h the product appeared as a yellowish precipitate and stirring was continued for further 1 h so that all of the reactants were converted into the product. The yellowish precipitate was filtered and collected. The product was dissolved in distilled ethanol (98%) by warming. Then the solution was filtered, allowed to cool and evaporated at room temperature to give square shaped white shining transparent crystals of (E) isomer suitable for single-crystal X-ray diffraction. The yellowish precipitate obtained initially may be due to the presence of both Z and E isomers. Recrystallization results in only E isomeric white shining transparent crys-

tals. Yield 93%, m.p. 265–269 °C; Anal. Calcd. (%) for C₂₁H₂₄N₆O₄: C, 59.42; H, 5.70; N, 19.80. Found: C, 59.45; H, 5.75; N, 19.78.

X-Ray data collection, reduction, structure solution and refinement of (E)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis(6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione) :

Single crystals of C₂₁H₂₄N₆O₄ (*E*-isomer) were recrystallized from ethanol. A suitable crystal (0.250 × 0.220 × 0.100 mm³) was selected and glued to a glass fiber on an Oxford Diffraction Xcalibur Eos Gemini ultra diffractometer equipped with graphite monochromator. The crystal was kept at 293 K during data collection. Data was analyzed with “CrysAlis PRO” software and the collected data was reduced by using the “CrysAlis PRO” program. An empirical absorption correction using spherical harmonics was implemented in ‘SCALE3 ABSPACK’ scaling algorithm. Using Olex2¹⁹, the structure was solved with the ShelXS²⁰ structure solution program, using the Direct Method solution method. The model was refined with the ShelXL²⁰ refinement package using Least Squares minimisation. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically, hydrogens on carbon were added from calculation. The crystallographic and experimental data are listed in Table 7.

The crystallographic information file has been deposited by us in the Cambridge structural database (CCDC-936043). These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data-request/cif, by E-mail : data-request@ccdc.com.ac.uk or by contacting the Cambridge CB21 EZ, UK; Fax : +44-1223-336033.

Antimicrobial assay :

The title compound was assessed for its *in vitro* antibacterial property against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria which include *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7816), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7814), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7812), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 7818), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 13607), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 11632), *Bacillus subtilis* (ATCC 11774) and antifungal activity against *Fusarium oxysporium* (MTCC 284) and *Candida albicans* (MTCC 227). Muller Hinton agar and sabouraud dextrose agar were employed for bacterial and fungal growth, respectively. The agar well diffusion technique was used in the present investigation, following the procedure de-

Table 7. Crystallographic detail of (*E*)-5,5'-(3-phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis[6-amino-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione]

Empirical formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄
Formula weight	424.46
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c
<i>a</i> (Å)	11.4666(9)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.3330(11)
<i>c</i> (Å)	14.7670(12)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	99.632(8)
γ (°)	90.00
Volume (Å ³)	2058.9(3)
Z	4
ρ_{calc} (mg/mm ³)	1.369
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.098
<i>F</i> (000)	896.0
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.25 × 0.22 × 0.1
2 θ range for data collection	5.32 to 50°
Index ranges	-13 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 13, -12 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 14, -17 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 16
Reflections collected	7785
Independent reflections	3619 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.0729]
Data/restraints/parameters	3619/0/284
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.977
Final <i>R</i> indexes [<i>I</i> > = 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0648, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.0915
Final <i>R</i> indexes [all data]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.1739, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1359

scribed by Boakye-Yiadom²¹, Banso and Adeyemo²² and Radhika *et al.*²³. 200 μ L of overnight grown culture (inoculum size was 10⁷–10⁸ cells/ml as per McFarland standard) of the test bacterial strains were seeded on the surface of the Muller Hinton agar while the fungal strains (0.5–2.5 × 10⁶/ml) were seeded on the sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) medium, using a sterile glass pipette and spreaded over the medium using a sterile glass spreader. A total of five numbers of wells, 6 mm each were made on solidified nutrient agar (NA) and sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) plates respectively, with the help of a sterile cork borer. Concentrations of 125, 250, 500, 1000 and 2000 μ g/ml of the synthesized compound dissolved in sterilized DMSO were introduced into each of the wells. Compounds at concentrations of 125–2000 μ g/ml were prepared in 10% DMSO (v/v). Streptomycin (1000 μ g/ml) and sterilized 10% DMSO (v/v) without the synthesized compound were taken as a positive and

negative control respectively for bacteria, and for fungi clotrimazole (1000 µg/ml) was used to serve as a positive control. Plates with a disc containing respective 10% DMSO (v/v) solvents also served as control. It was found that DMSO showed no effect against the microorganisms under test. In case of bacteria, the plates were incubated at 37 ± 2 °C for 24 h while for fungal cultures; the plates were kept at 27 ± 2 °C for 48 h. The observed zones of inhibition were measured using transparent metric ruler. The experiment was done thrice and the mean values were determined. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the synthesized compounds was determined by the micro dilution method and compared to broad-spectrum antibiotics. MIC is defined as the lowest concentration of compound that inhibited visible growth of the test organism.

All the compounds after experiment for antimicrobial studies were disposed according to the guidelines laid down by Institute Bio-safety committee.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have successfully studied the (*E*) isomer of the targeted compound by analysing the single crystal X-ray crystallography, IR, NMR and UV spectroscopy. The magnetically non-equivalent uracil moieties of bis-uracil derivative (**A**) display a dihedral angle of $60.44(14)^\circ$ and centroids distance is $5.069(2)$ Å. It is observed that N-H...O hydrogen bonds, weak C-H...O and π - π stacking interactions may be responsible for the stability of the compound (**A**) and its bioactivity. From the preliminary antimicrobial studies, it is found that the compound (**A**) is biologically active. The further biological studies of this title compound like cell line and theoretical studies are in progress and these may lend new direction for future work.

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